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Departamento
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PROYECTO I+D

LEILA

APRENDIZAJE DE LENGUAS EXTRANJERAS
Y LENGUAS ADICIONALES EN LA INFANCIA

LANGUAGE TEACHING PRACTICES IN MEXICAN SCHOOLS

- Mexico: plurilingual and multicultural
- 90% Spanish users
- 68 linguistic groupings
- More 364 variants (7.5 mil)
- Language learning in schools
- Nothing similar to European scenario

POLICIES

- National programme of English language instruction in the Mexican public primary schools, (PNIEB) 2009, reformed 2011
- *Programa Nacional de Inglés en la Educación Básica (PRONI)*, 2017–18, regulates English instruction in compulsory education throughout the country.
- Extended *Estrategia Nacional de Inglés*, July 2017

PRONI

- Inclusion of compulsory 3rd pre-primary education (5-6 years)
- English language instruction compulsory but **NOT** part of the national curricular plan
- 1,060 and 1,900 hours of English classes per educational cycle

- Very different context: no specific policies, methodologies, curriculum or resources *per se*
- PRONI generated a myriad of practices
- 2, 2.5 h/week/group
- Reached 18% population
- No specific official curriculum
- Limited materials, free?
- Teachers' employment status, training
- English teachers for pre-primary and primary ed

- ▣ Teachers' narratives and views
- ▣ Qualitative approach “
- ▣ Data collection: semi-structured interviews
- ▣ Analysing cases from different regions of Mx, central
- ▣ Experiences collected from practitioners

Project expanded: **LEYLA** Design of a teacher profile for pre-primary Education from a plurilingual approach: learning foreign and additional languages in early childhood

Researchers: 16 Spanish, 11 international

Early language learning, Teachers' competencies, create a teachers' competencies framework

Discussion groups from many countries

Focus on
Teachers' narratives and views
(initial interviews)

S1

- Start pre-literacy + English from pre-K
- 85% English (music, maths, sciences, computing...)
- Lingua franca English
- Translanguaging happens
- Training in English teaching
- Project based + phonics

S2

- Exposure to English from 3 y. o.
- Pre-writing: 5 y.o.
- AMCO, Advanced Method Company
- Language skills, storytelling, pronunciation lab, pre-maths & arts
- Specific teacher training

S3

- SISTEMA UNOi
- Preschool through Bachiller
- Pre-schoolers: 6h of English p/w
- Pictures, no text, very simple vocabulary
- Students: daily life in/out of school, use Spanish

S4

- Public *Jardín de niños*.
- Small school: 4 groups of 25
- Not eligible for PRONI (m. 35) 3rd preschool
- BUT appointed English teacher
- 10 h/group in the whole school year
- Textbook: everyday situations, frequent topics, songs, rhymes, Mexican flora and fauna...
- Difficulties, after COVID never again

S5

- Public preschool
- PRONI program for two years
- Granted 1h English class / group a week
- Teachers: create materials, plan course, use materials and media provided
- Feel students fall short in exposure to the language

CONCLUSIONS

English:

- Public schools: 2/3 h week

- Private schools: 60-80%

- Common thread: program nicely designed, clear objectives (assure English learning). Infrastructure not motivating.

- Private institutions

- stable staff, training, common methodology...)

CONCLUSIONS

Public schools:

- ▣ More training needed
- ▣ Needing long term programs
- ▣ Uncertainty for teachers, working conditions, drop-outs
- ▣ Uncertainty for schools
- ▣ Unpredictability for PRONI.....

CONCLUSIONS

- ▣ Teachers' voices: results affected by public programs, teaching conditions, T. training, context & curricular flexibility (private s.).

- ▣ Language teaching happening:
 - ▣ Private intitutions
 - ▣ Public: introduction of English as additional language (difficulties).

- “Mexico might face additional barriers in implementing a CLT approach, given the large class sizes and limited resources”.
Na, Gregory & Téllez (2021)
- Key promises unfulfilled due to context as policies political or economic reasons
- Public policies: teachers are willing to participate but, hesitant about their implementation

IMPLICATIONS

- ▣ Impertative decisión makers, federal/state level, regarding EFL programs, move towards long term programs...
- ▣ Consistently implement programs
- ▣ Move forward CLIL framework

“

Changes are building up slowly
although the road is long.

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Thank
you